

Life Skills

Using text-to-speech browser feature to read and reply to email using the webmail client

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Life Skills

Using text-to-speech
browser
feature to read
the news
website

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free
features?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Life Skills

Using text-to-speech browser feature to read the top 3 posts in the social network news feed

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Life Skills

Using text-to-speech browser feature, zoom feature and/or magnifier to find train schedule in website

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

More free features?

Help?

Simpler processes?

Life Skills

TRANSLATE

Use language translator in email to understand words in foreign languages

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

Life Skills

Use language translator on news websites to understand words in foreign languages

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

Life Skills

Use language translator to understand words in foreign languages on Social Network feeds

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Simpler processes?

Help?

Life Skills

Obtain
COVID-19
certificate
online

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
microphone?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Life Skills

Confirm emergency contacts

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
microphone?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

Life Skills

**Buy food
online**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Integrated
microphone?

Help?

Simpler
processes?

